

KNOWLEDGE AND DIDACTIC APPROACH OF GIFTED PEOPLE*

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Abstract

A first step in approaching gifted people is to identify them, and this aspect was the factor that led to the initiation of this study. The next step after a first identification is the specific knowledge itself to build a proper interaction.

Such an approach was carried out through the analysis of our own experience in university education, in particular, in the psycho-pedagogical training for the teaching profession, an activity, in which we had the opportunity to meet adults who have obvious characteristics of high endowment in terms of intellectual capacities and learning performances.

Essentially, our article includes four case studies that bring to the fore how giftedness manifests itself in adult students, with different study paths and life contexts. The data presented were corroborated with an overall analysis of the results of the academic activity of these people, as past or present results, necessary to establish which are the differentiated and appropriate teaching approaches.

The learning behaviours characteristic of gifted people include in-depth treatment of tasks, reveal links among the invoked experiences, include personal reflections, work in variants and are oriented by long-term interests.

The results obtained show that, through approaches favourable to self-knowledge, by stimulating group interaction, adult learners with giftedness can realistically appreciate their potential, give up perfectionism, convergent, constructivist channel their critical-creative interventions in academic learning.

Key words: *Intellectual giftedness, Adult students, Learning, Results, Differentiated approach.*

1. What is the intellectual giftedness and how does it manifest itself in the academic environment

The concept of giftedness evolved from a psychometric perspective, centered on the knowledge of the intelligence quotient of gifted children, compared to ordinary

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children, in America (Terman, 1925), to multidimensional models, developed by combining data discovered at international level, which took into account the role of creativity factors, motivation and context for the development of talent.

The identification of giftedness has often been considered a predictor of people's success in academia.

After a systematization of the recent literature, Delgado-Valencia et al. (2025) showed that the identification of giftedness should be based on methods that prioritize the existence of general cognitive abilities, their developmental history, to the detriment of measured intelligence scores and academic results obtained.

Thus, we can understand giftedness as a complex construct, which arises from the interaction among higher cognitive abilities, personality traits and educational opportunities, according to the main authors who have been concerned with the analysis of this theme (in Sternberg & Davidson, 2005).

Gifted and talented people are capable of high performance, demonstrating acquisitions and/or skills such as: general intellectual capacity, specific academic aptitude, productive thinking, creativity, ability to be a leader, etc.

Regarding the motivation for self-training, Carré, Moisan, Poisson (2010) emphasized the decisive role of representations about the future, of proactivity, understood as engagement in the self-determined act, but also of the necessary adjustments to be applied through metacognitive activities, which intervene in the instrumentation of the elements of intentional dynamics.

In 2023, Reynen-Woodward, Round and Subban presented a synthesis of research that drew attention to the facilitating role that university education plays for gifted young people from disadvantaged backgrounds, showing that if they are not successful at this level of training, factors such as poverty and belonging to a minority culture create exclusion for the gifted.

2. Giftedness, a contextual perspective

The complexity of this aptitude is highlighted by many authors, for example, Renzulli (in Sternberg & Davidson, 2005, pp. 246-279), who proposed a three-ring model approach, considering that giftedness occurs at the intersection between:

- a) above-average cognitive abilities;
- b) creativity;
- c) commitment to task.

The identification as giftedness can be unanimous, general, or it can be carried out for a specific field, therefore, we also find at an empirical level that, without being tested from the point of view of the intelligence quotient, young children, pupils, students – be they young, adults, elderly – classified as gifted are intellectually remarkable and can excel in certain fields, not in all of them.

In Romania, two important authors of the field, Crețu (1997) and Jigău (2004) have contributed to clarifying the phenomenon of giftedness, emphasizing the difference between giftedness (seen as a high general intellectual capacity) and talent (which refers to specific skills).

Another perspective worth to be remembered is that of Gagné (2004), who emphasized the idea that harnessing hereditary potential (gifts) in order to perform is possible by training skills, emphasizing the role of the environment and intrapersonal catalyts.

The promoter of multiple intelligences, Gardner (1993), has shown for some time that there are several types of intelligence, and each person has his or her strengths, beyond the recognized logical-mathematical intelligence, therefore, the personalized approach is likely to facilitate performance.

Essentially, the characteristics associated with giftedness are:

- accelerated cognitive development;
- superior visual and verbal memory;
- early metacognitive ability;
- high creativity;
- intrinsic motivation for learning;
- increased emotional sensitivity and asynchrony in personality development.

However, these characteristics are not universally present, as gifted people do not form a homogeneous group, but one with a great diversity of cognitive and emotional profiles, the identification and treatment being multifactorial (Dumitrescu, 2004).

The role of the environment and differentiated treatment is essential in the special approach of the gifted, as noted by Popovici and Balotă (2004), explaining that the stages of development to which we refer are very relevant, so that, if, at the age of adolescence, the gifted experiences a situation of school failure or underachievement, the self-image will be a negative one, with serious consequences for adult life.

We can say that gifted students learn differently, and the differences in learning are also determined by the category of learners, young people or adults. From our point of view, the possibilities of self-management are even more present at students who are oriented towards independent study, who have formed learning/intellectual work skills, who have autonomy in learning (Ștefan, 2014).

The good self-knowledge, self-planning, self-organization and self-regulation are actions that improve academic efficiency (Frăsineanu, 2012) and that contribute to in-depth learning (Frăsineanu, 2013).

At youth (between 18/20-35 years old) the stage of formal operations is installed, the ability to solve abstract problems, to make hypothetical-deductive reasoning, to systematically evaluate specific solutions is developed. Thus, young people are, on the level of cognitive evolution, in the last stage of formal operations of thought, but not all adults have a complete operative structure either.

Given the specificity of higher education training, in which the basic element is specialization in a field, a large part of the knowledge structures assimilated during the school years are no longer used.

As for the way they learn, compared to young people, at adults (people between 35-65 years old), a concentrated and economical learning attitude equals the learning pace, which is lower, while the assumed motivation of learning compensates for the

weakening of memory. Learning opportunities are influenced by social factors, related to life history and the concerns about obtaining professional expertise.

The qualities of adult learners are worthy of appreciation: intrapsychic stability acquired over time, emotional management, responsible choices, social commitment, desire to surpass oneself, willingness to resume learning, interlearning.

3. Advantages and difficulties of gifted people

It is certain that gifted people have a series of traits that constitute advantages, but they also face a series of difficulties, as we have summarized, in accordance with the ideas of some theorists and researchers in the field, in the following table:

Table 1. Advantages and disadvantages of giftedness

Advantages of giftedness	Authors	Disadvantages of giftedness	of Authors
superior processing and learning speed	Winner, 1996	risk of underperformance in unfavourable educational environments	Reis & McCoach, 2000
strong intrinsic motivation for areas of interest	Renzulli, 2012	asynchronous development	Silverman, 2013
advanced metacognitive skills	Neihart, Pfeiffer & Cross, 2016	anxiety and increased emotional sensitivity	Neihart, Pfeiffer & Cross, 2016
high creativity and divergent thinking	Sternberg, 2018	non-adaptive perfectionism	Chen, Flett & Hewitt, 2019

In view of the main advantages and disadvantages listed, the family, school, social media or professional integration will act to correctly identify gifted people and to apply strategies to: intervention in order to increase their learning performance; maintaining motivation and achieving psychological well-being.

Various countries, such as the USA, the Netherlands, Israel or South Korea, have clear educational policies on identifying and supporting the gifted (OECD, 2021), in which the focus is on: early interventions, application of advanced programs in universities, support for socio-emotional development, training of teachers to work with people with special educational needs, including through forms of mentoring or teamwork, project realization or involvement in advanced research.

It is worth mentioning the existence of profiles of "double exceptionality" (Lewis & Milam, 2026; Baum, Renzulli & Jobe, 2026), which refers to the coexistence of giftedness and learning difficulties or emotional disorders.

Teachers' creativity must be activated to allow students to express their creativity, stay focused and interested in classes, as in Romania, especially, there are no clear statistics related to the situation of young people or adults who have an IQ above 130, and concerns are focused on detecting people under the age of 18.

4. Organization and implementation of micro-research investigation

An important premise in approaching learners with giftedness in learning, also mentioned in the literature of the field, was to pay attention to their abilities, relating to giftedness as a developing expertise (Sternberg, 2001).

The initial sample of our research was made up of all the students with whom we interacted directly and in a very sustained manner during the academic year 2025-2026, within the academic training of young people and adults in the psycho-pedagogical field, in a state university in southwestern Romania.

Out of 597 students (267 students in the first semester and 330 students in the second semester), we noticed 4 full-time students, one woman and three men, who had an above-average learning performance, admirable during the courses and seminars.

Their level of preparation and learning skills were unanimously appreciated, both by us, as a teacher, and by their colleagues. Also, the categorization as giftedness was certified by the quantitative data existing in their study documents, as will be observed, in what will follow later, in the synthetic table no. 2.

Therefore, the 4 students represented the actual sample on which we focused, in order to identify the skills, capacities, particularities that represent each one, as an adult, because, from the point of view of the category of student, they fell into the age category over 35 years old.

Our investigation and the research idea were designed in order to establish certain lines of action as favourable as possible to capitalize on the potential they had at the time we met them. Thus, we met two of the four people in October 2025, and two others in February 2026.

The hypotheses we established were:

Hypothesis 1: It is possible that people gifted to learn in general (in their field of specialization, including in the field of psycho-pedagogical training) have a low awareness of their own abilities and some difficulties of socio-emotional manifestation.

Hypothesis 2: If people gifted to learn in the academic environment are approached in a personalized way, by encouraging the critical-creative approach, by affirming themselves in public, by supporting curricular enrichment, then qualitative improvements in learning behaviours will be obtained: gifted people will better capitalize on their creative ideas and critical interventions, will overcome social evaluation anxiety, will learn additionally, deep, independent.

The research methods used were combined and used selectively, in order to create a relevant cut-off for the profile of our subjects: observation, micro-case studies, autobiographical method, conversation, analysis of curricular documents (study transcripts), analysis of the products of the activity (written works, applied works).

5. Results obtained and discussions

In relation to the level of education and other characteristics present in the subjects of the investigation, we mention that:

- two subjects are pursuing bachelor's studies in the first year, in the field of Social Sciences, for an extension of their initial training path (one, from a completely different field, the field of Engineering Sciences), although they

are already graduates of bachelor's, master's and doctoral studies, being employed and recognized professionally (W, man – 44 years old; X, woman – 43 years old);

- one subject follows bachelor's studies in the first year, in the field of Human Sciences and Arts, being an adult who is professionally employed, as a graduate of bachelor's and doctoral study programs in the basic field (Y, male – 59 years old);
- one subject follows master's studies in the second year, in the Advanced Techniques for Information Process specialization, after completing a professional activity in the army (Z, male – 56 years old).

The four adults are each married and have children.

Keeping the anonymity of personal data and applying minimal interventions was an ethical priority for us in knowing, but also in interacting with people who have characteristics of giftedness, a priority that we respected, so as not to create discriminatory comparisons in the series to which the students belong.

We also specify that, beyond the well-deserved appraisals of us and their colleagues, it was considered very useful, in all cases, at a technical or procedural level, those constructive, more detailed evaluations, for concrete aspects, which are overlooked, on the part of gifted subjects.

From an attitudinal perspective, encouraging realistic self-evaluation and self-identification of over-perfectionism have proven their effectiveness, as we have found that, in the academic environment, gifted people can be misunderstood by others, given their thinking style (more abstract, profound, with decision-making speed, critical, creative, divergent approach) or through exacerbations of introversion or extraversion.

An analysis of the course by levels of study and of the general averages or current grades obtained by the subjects, taken from their curricular documents, highlights a confirmation of the learning competences through the results obtained.

Table 2. Quantitative performance in the subjects' years of study

Topic	Quantitative results of years of study
W	Bachelor's degree: average 8.98; Master's degree: average 9.94; Graduate doctoral studies; Average in the first semester, first year of current study: 10 (ten); Average 9.66 at the psycho-pedagogical training program for the teaching profession; Observations: difficulties encountered in the recognition of the graduated doctoral studies, the advantage of international professional training internships, stands out through the hyperactive, extroverted personality type, leadership qualities, assertive, has an international recognition of specialized contributions, has gone through various study paths, connected with the main field of training and activity.
X	Two graduate bachelor's degree programs; Master's degree: average: 10 (ten);

Completed doctoral studies:

Average in the first semester, first year of current study: 10 (ten);

Average 10 (ten) in the psycho-pedagogical training program for the teaching profession;

Observations: he has completed training courses in Europe and has an international recognition at professional level, he can speak English well, he has multiple academic interests and he has gone through various study paths, connected with the main field of training and activity.

Y Two graduate bachelor's degree programs;

Completed doctoral studies;

Average in the first semester, first year of current study, for twelve subjects: 9.75;

Grade 10 (ten) so far in the psycho-pedagogical training program for the teaching profession (one subject);

Observations: rich learning experience, following the completion of international study internships; has gone through various paths of study, different from the main field of training and activity; it is, as an extroverted personality type; sociable, agreeable; She has extensive professional experience, solid general culture with inter- and cross-cultural perspectives.

Z Bachelor's degree: average 9.68;

Average at the end of the first semester, for the first and second years of current study, as an average of fifteen subjects: 9.95;

Average 10 (ten) so far in the psycho-pedagogical training program for the teaching profession (several subjects);

Observations: although he is perceived by colleagues or other teachers as a student with very good results, who actively participates in academic activities, the performance, communication, interaction in the university environment are marked by self-confidence, fear of public expression; His socialization is restricted. The person does not highlight his existing abilities and abilities to the fullest, but only if he is encouraged to assert themselves.

In the case of subject X, a woman, 43 years old, the person is very well integrated professionally and appreciated by the beneficiaries or the supervised staff, but still manifests some fears regarding the ability to get involved in new projects, in unknown situations, as a fear of failure.

The result of the indirect evaluation, in writing, as well as direct, face to face, indicated the correct mastery of the notions of study, the possession of the skills in the evaluated field, a rich general and specialized culture.

The explanations for this situation correlate with the increased level of effort required in several areas of her life and with a certain internalization, characteristic shyness, tendency towards perfectionism.

In the case of subject Z, a 56-year-old man, we notice a minimum level of self-confidence and a lack of external encouragement. Also, although he is very conscientious and can put forward solid arguments, in cases of critical debates he is sensitive, withdrawn, without assertive power.

This time, the explanations for this situation are related to the lack of exercise to participate in oral debates or a spontaneous academic discourse, low resistance to frustration, predominantly reflective thinking style, modesty in self-appreciation.

Hypothesis 1 was confirmed because, although at the other two adults (W, Y, males, 44 years old and 59 years old, respectively), the socio-emotional abilities and assertive capacities are evident, they are part of the very personality structure that they have formed, as a result of training in previous professional or study situations.

Even if they successfully overcame obstacles in life and learning, the subjects reported that, most of the time, they were unsure of the quality of their answers and results, waiting for external confirmation. So, uncertainties, emotional hypersensitivity and excessive perfectionism manifest themselves, but they can be overcome.

Hypothesis 2 focused on the conduct that teachers can have, by orienting the critical-creative approach towards results obtained in a constructivist manner, by encouraging open debates between gifted students and their peers, by self-corrections and restructuring of the experience, by supporting curricular developments.

We could see that gifted people made progress from the initial stage (from the beginning of the semester to the final, at the end of the semester) in capitalizing on creative ideas, oral interventions, the quality of independently developed projects, but also an increase in collaboration with colleagues, being able to approach learning in an in-depth, independent, enriched and shared manner.

Thus, we can consider that hypothesis 2 was confirmed, because, in carrying out the tasks of the applicative work, essay/project we identified the achievement of implicit standards: the presence of curiosity, the manifestation of independence in thinking, persistence in solving the requirements, the capitalization of external feedback by restructuring the answers and the complexity of the ideas elaborated.

Challenging tasks energize the learners and prevent boredom, decreased motivation or even positively channel behavioural overexcitability, increased enthusiasm identifiable in the case of subject W.

The results demonstrated in the written exam papers, as a reflection of their intellectual plan, were excellent in each of the four subjects, from an analytical, creative, but also pragmatic point of view. For three of them we found that there is a preference for analytical and creative processuality, through mental flexibility and fluidity of ideas, and the subject who has professional experience and patents in the technical field managed to add a practical rationality to his academic answers.

6. Identified limits and discussions

Although the qualitative and quantitative results on the cases of gifted students, presented above, indicate an increased level of resilience in academic learning and in socio-professional manifestations, it is possible that through our analyses we have not fully and fully known their situation.

Even though the sample consisted of a small number of subjects, our study focused on the possibilities of supporting gifted people, who have different training and life paths. These limits of the sample, naturally constituted within a Panel micro-

research, have, compared to large, longitudinal studies, methodological, time and spatial representativeness limits.

However, the combination of several investigative modalities has been useful for establishing subtle ways of influencing in order to capitalize on the potential available to gifted people.

In addition, other recent research supports the importance of developing a growth mindset, perseverance, commitment to tasks or motivation in learners, components that condition academic achievement (Acheampong, 2025; Mărincaș, Trif & Opre, 2025).

The perseverance is a key factor in obtaining certain results, and „Initially, the perseverance was conceptualized in two facets – consistency of interest (commitment and passion in pursuing the goals) and perseverance of effort (the mental toughness to keep working under pressure)” (Duckwort et al., 2007, cited by Lam & Zhou, 2025, p. 2).

Consequently, the complexity of the factors that act in harnessing the potential of gifted people leaves room for the identification of other cases, not only among adult students, but also among young students.

7. Conclusions and openings

The success-oriented mentality, motivational determination or perseverance, but also external support are important factors in capitalizing on the learning potential that gifted people have.

Through our micro-research, we have revealed that gifted adults, studying in higher education, manifest in performance in learning, originality, a level of maturity and interest, which allows them to further improve and which requires differentiated and individualized approaches applied consistently.

For the future, it is important that such cases to be correctly identified, that they are properly supported, in order to eliminate situations of underachievement (Peña-San José, Arruti & Martínez-Izaguirre, 2026) – as a discrepancy between the existing high potential and the results obtained. Developing self-efficacy in academic learning by gifted learners is a strategy that can be pursued further.

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